

The Boson Statistical Enhancement Factor $1+\langle n(e_i) \rangle$

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 14, 2026

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ may be thought of in terms of $\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-e_3/T)\exp(-e_4/T)$ if $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ ((1)), but if one multiplies this by NN , where N is the number of particles, then $N_1*N_2=N_3*N_4$, i.e. one considers the different number of ways an E_1 may collide with an E_2 and equates this to the number of ways an E_3 may collide with an E_4 . If one considers this as a kind of principle, then in the case of photons one has $\langle n(e_i) \rangle$, but even though $e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4$ and $\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-e_3/T)\exp(-e_4/T)$, $\langle n(e_1) \rangle \langle n(e_2) \rangle \neq \langle n(e_3) \rangle \langle n(e_4) \rangle$. In other words, it seems like the key idea is really $\exp(-e_i/T)$ such that ((1)) holds. In such a case, if one wishes to work with $\langle n(e_i) \rangle$, which does appear in photon calculations, but only as an outcome of the notion of $\exp(-e_i/T)$, then one must somehow convert $\langle n(e_i) \rangle$ into $\exp(-e_i/T)$. We suggest that this is really what happens with the photon enhancement factor $1+\langle n(e_i) \rangle = 1/(1-\exp(-e_i/T))$. In other words, one could simply focus on ((1)).

Maxwell-Boltzmann Problem

The Maxwell-Boltzmann problem may be solved using the fundamental idea of a

$$p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_k)p(e_l) \text{ for } e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l \text{ ((1))}$$

This leads to $p(e_i) = C\exp(-e_i/T)$ as a solution. ((1)) has the form of AND probabilities as would arise in two body collisions. Thus,

$$N\exp(-e_i/T) = \text{the number of independent particles with energy } e_i \text{ ((2))}$$

In such a case:

$$n(e_i)n(e_j) = n(e_k)n(e_l) \text{ for } e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l \text{ ((3))}$$

A photon case also has an $n(e_i)$ value, but unfortunately this does not represent a number of independent photons. We suggest that the fundamental statistical idea present is ((1)) and that this still holds for a photon. The objective is to convert $n(e_i)$ into $\exp(-e_i/T)$, we argue.

The Photon Case

The fundamental statistical idea use in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case is the probability

$$\exp(-e_i/T) \text{ associated with an energy } e_i \text{ ((4))}$$

Given that photons have electric fields which add, one may have as many photons as one wants at a point x because through energy which is not equal to the $.5 \epsilon_0$ multiplied by

the total electric field (plus the magnetic piece), one still knows the identity of the photons. For a particle with rest mass (ignoring spin), one cannot superimpose two rest masses m_0 at the same x point and argue that one knows there are two masses because the energy is the same as a single particle with $2m_0$. As a result, photons are special and one must consider the probability:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Sum over } i=0 \text{ to infinite } P(i \text{ photons with energy } e_1) &= \text{Sum over } i=0, \text{ infinite } \exp(-e_i/T * n) \\ &= 1/(1-\exp(-e_i/T)) \quad ((5)) \end{aligned}$$

Then:

$$n(e_i) = d/dy ((5)) = \exp(-y) / (1-\exp(-y)) \quad \text{where } y=e_i/T \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{This implies that } ((5)) = 1+n(e_i) \quad ((7))$$

As a result, one has $n(e_i)$ values, but this does not represent independent photons available for a collision. We caution against trying to equate:

$$n(e_1)n(e_2) \text{ with } n(e_3)n(e_4) \quad ((7))$$

An equal sign does not hold for ((7)) like it does for the Maxwell-Boltzman case. Rather, one requires:

$$\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-e_3/T)\exp(-e_4/T) \quad ((8))$$

((8)) does not include $n(e_i)$. It seems, however, that $n(e_i)$ appears in statistical physics expressions and this leads to the notion of a boson enhancement factor. Here, we try to see how one may arrive at ((8)) using the notion of $n(e_i)$. One may formally see from ((6)) that:

$$n(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) (1+n(e_i)) \quad ((7))$$

It is this equation then that appears in a reaction balance as:

$$n(e_1) (1+n(e_3)) n(e_2) (1+n(e_4)) = n(e_3) (1+n(e_1)) n(e_4) (1+n(e_2)) \quad ((8))$$

Using ((7)), however, one may see that $n(e_i)$ divided by $1+n(e_i)$ restores $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

We try to consider two examples to see how this happens.

Case 1

Consider $.9 = \exp(-e_1/T)$.

Then:

$$\text{Probability (n=0 to 4)} = 1 + .9 + .81 + .6 + .36 = 3.67$$

$$n \cdot \text{probability for n=0 to 4} = .9 + 1.61 + 1.8 + 1.44 = 5.75$$

$$n(e_i) = 5.75 / 3.67 = 1.56$$

$$\text{and } n(e_i) / (1 + n(e_i)) = .42$$

We started with $\exp(-e_1/T) = .9$ and so $n=0$ to 4 does not provide a very accurate value, but it does show that $n(e_i)$ is reigned in and that one must be careful when considering $n(e_i)$ in terms of reactions.

$$\text{Formally, } 1 + n(e_1) = 1 / (1 - \exp(-e_1/T)) = 1 / (1 - .9) = 10 \text{ and } n(e_i) = .9 \cdot 10 = 9$$

It seems, nevertheless, that $n(e_i)$ is reigned in in order to convert it to $\exp(-e_i/T)$. Thus, $n(e_i)$ does not seem to be the physical quantity of interest, but $\exp(-e/T)$.

Case 2

$$\text{The second example uses } \exp(-e/T) = \exp(-2) = .135$$

$$\text{Probability}(n=0, 3) = 1 + .135 + .018 + .00246 = 1.15546$$

$$n \cdot \text{probability} = .135 + .036 + .007 = .178$$

$$n(e_i) = .154 \text{ Formally, this is } .135 / (1 - .135) = .156$$

$$\text{Then } .154 / 1.15546 = .135 \text{ which is equal to } \exp(-e/T)$$

In this case the numbers work much better because $n(e_i)$ is very small and one does not have to reign it in as in the first case. Again, $n(e_i)$ is reigned in.

Physical Interaction Scenario

In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, one has $N_1 = N \cdot \exp(-e_1/T)$. This means that there are N_1 e_1 particles spaced throughout the system. Such is not the case with photons, because they are bunched. One might have 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 etc. Given $n(e_i)$, this does not mean that one has $n(e_i)$ e_1 photons spread out equally through space. The number $n(e_i)$ includes the notion of bunching and so one cannot consider it as representing the number of ways a collision may occur independently in space due to this bunching, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Maxwell-Boltzmann calculation is based on the fundamental idea of $\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-e_3/T)\exp(-e_4/T)$ if $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ ((9)). Multiplying by NN (N =number of particles) one has $N_1*N_2=N_3*N_4$. The fundamental idea ((9)) also applies to photons, but unlike particles with mass m_0 (ignoring spin) one can place as many photons at the same x point as one wished because the electric fields add, but the total energy is not $.5e_0$ total electric field * total electric field plus the magnetic field contribution. For a particle with rest mass, two m_0 's at the same x have the same energy as a single $2m_0$ if there is no spin to distinguish. Given that one may place as many photons at the same x , one has a different calculation for photons as probability is $\text{Sum over } i \exp(-e_i/T * n)$ where $n=0$ to infinite. One may calculate an $n(e_1)$, but this is an average and does not represent independent photons ready to interact (so to speak). Thus, we caution against focusing too much on statistical balance equations which use $n(e_i)$. $n(e_i)$ includes the bunching of photons and so does not represent the number of e_i photons spread out over space. Ultimately one wishes to use the fundamental idea ((9)) and if $n(e_i)$ is present, it must be converted into $\exp(-e_i/T)$. This is done through $\exp(-e_i/T) = n(e_i) / (1+n(e_i))$. We provides two numerical examples to show how the factor $1+n(e_i)$ tries to reign in $n(e_i)$ in order to obtain $\exp(-e_i/T)$ which is the basic quantity of interest, we argue.